

OPTIMISING THE MECHANICAL PROPERTIES OF 3D-KNITTED SANDWICH STRUCTURES

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SUMMARY: In this paper an overview is given of the newest developments on 3D-knitted composites. The main effort has been focussed on overcoming the problems of translating the knittings from a textile environment to the field of composites. The major developments are going on in the development and use of complex yarns. Also, the first results of bending tests on different kinds of 3D-knitted composites are presented. The main parameters seem to be the orientation of the beam elements and the areal density of the composite. However, it is not easy to compare all results since a lot of parameters are involved. To overcome this, a new normalisation method will be necessary and more tests results are required.

KEYWORDS: knittings, sandwich, preforms

INTRODUCTION

In the last few years the interest for composites based on knittings has increased significantly due to the extremely good drapability of knitted prepregs and because complex parts can be shaped quite easily even with a reduced number of processing steps.

The new material described in this paper is based on two existing types of composite. It combines the advantages of the integrally 3D-woven sandwich structures[1] with the deformability and handleability of knitted preforms[2]. It is thought that this approach can have some advantages compared to the more traditional sandwich structures.

Currently, most sandwich structures are produced by bonding together two skins onto a core material. However, core materials with high specific properties such as honeycombs and some special types of foam are very expensive and hence, the complete sandwich becomes quite expensive as well. In the case of textile reinforcements such as the 3D-knitted and 3D-woven sandwich fabrics, the cost can be significantly lower because of the well-known textile technologies and the low cost mass production of these textiles[3].

Another typical problem which is difficult to solve with classical sandwich structures is the delamination of the skins, especially when the sandwich has been damaged. By using integral 3D-knitted and 3D-woven sandwich composites, this problem can be prevented.

One of the main advantages of these 3D-knitted structures is that double-curved sandwich panels can be produced easily. This is not really possible with the current sandwich materials and thus 3D-knitted sandwich composites bring a new feature to this class of materials.

CONCEPT & PRODUCTION OF 3D-KNITTINGS

Concept

3D-knitted sandwich fabrics consist of two skins [4], which look like a grid of knitted beam elements in a hexagonal or a rhombic configuration. The top and bottom skin of the knit are attached to each other by pile fibers standing vertical to the fabric plane. These pile fibers act as a core for the sandwich structure. Their length can be adjusted to modify the fabric thickness and hence also the composite properties.

Fig. 1: Hexagonal grid structure of a 3D-knitting

Fig. 2: Close look at the pile fibers

Production

The production of 3D-knittings is very similar to that of flat knittings. Only here, in principle, two knitting machines are put back to back in order to produce the top and the bottom skins of the sandwich fabric simultaneously. In practice, a double-bed rashell knitting machine is used for this purpose. This machine has two needle beds that can be controlled independently.

Fig. 3: Schematic drawing of the knitting process

During the knitting process the skins are being connected with pile fibers. These fibers not only constitute the core of the fabric but they are also part of the skins. This can be seen in Fig. 3 where it is shown how the piles are knitted into the top skin of the fabric. In the next

production step, the pile fibers will be drawn downwards and they will be used together with the skin yarns to knit one more loop of the bottom skin. It is clear that the pile fibers make up an integral part of the skins and it will be difficult to delaminate the skins from the core.

OPTIMISING THE KNITTINGS FOR COMPOSITE APPLICATIONS

Basic problems

The open 3D-knittings which were first used for producing composite samples are types that have been developed for textile applications only. These samples were all knitted with PET-monofilament yarns and after some exploratory investigation it became clear that these plain PET-monofilament knittings needed some adaptation before being qualified for composite applications.

First of all, there is already a contradiction for selecting the right yarns for knitting. From a knitting point of view, a flexible yarn is needed to produce small but complex loops with high curvature. In this case a multifilament yarn is recommended. However, when this knit has to be impregnated and draped over a complex surface. It has to keep a stable geometry and the skins need to stay at a distance from each other in order not to loose the sandwich effect. So in this case a stiffer monofilament yarn is required although this yarn may not be too stiff or the needles will break during knitting.

The picture becomes more complex when impregnation characteristics are considered too. Multifilaments can be impregnated better, easier and more homogenous than monofilaments as can be clearly seen in Fig. 4 and Fig. 5.

Fig. 4: Homogenous impregnation of pile fibers

Fig.5: Poor impregnation of pile fibers

All these problems can be solved by combining multi and monofilament yarns. The basic idea is the following. One central thin PET-monofilament is wrapped with lots of other fibers so that the combined fiber is still very flexible for knitting. The central monofilament provides the geometrical stability of the knit during impregnation while the multifilaments improve the impregnation quality but they can also increase the mechanical properties of the composite if stiffer fibers like glass or ramie are used. The multifilaments can have two effects on the resin. The network of cavities between the fibers can take up a lot of resin because of capillarity while the some fibers can absorb resin by themselves (i.e. ramie).

*Fig. 6: Combined PET/ramie-viscose yarn **Improving the mechanical properties***

Bending properties

Because of the very open structure we cannot expect the mechanical properties of the knitted sandwich composite to be extremely high. Nevertheless, the material performance can be optimised and several options are available to reach this goal.

First of all, the geometry can be adapted by changing the type of unit cell. Cell size can be reduced also to increase the effective surface area of the fabric and to increase the amount of material in the skins. Consequently this will increase the density of the material too. Another possibility is to stretch the knit before impregnating, so that the beam elements in the fabric become more oriented in one direction (Fig. 7, Fig. 8). Of course this will make the composite behave more anisotropic.

Fig. 7: Highly stretched knitted composite (18°) Fig. 8: Less stretched knitted composite (33°)

A second alternative is to make the composite stiffer by using stiffer yarns. This was first done by introducing ramie-viscose into the skins. The next step was to include glass fibers but knitting glass into the skins is already much more difficult. The glass fibers easily break

because of the high tension on the knitting yarns and because of high curvatures inside the knitting loops. Another option is not to knit the glass but to insert the glass fibers as straight bundles in the skins.

Compression & impact

To increase the compression and impact resistance of the composite, the load bearing capacity of the pile fibers has to become higher. This means that the buckling resistance of each single pile has to get better. With the introduction of combined yarns for pile fibers a major improvement has been realised.

By increasing the density of pile fibers the load experienced by a single pile can be reduced so that the overall compression and impact properties of the composite can improve.

BENDING PROPERTIES

Description of the fabrics used

Table1: Description of 3D-knittings

Knit	Geometry	Pile Fiber	Skin Fiber	Skin Inserts
H10	Hexagonal	PETmonofil	PETmonofil	-
R7	Rhombic	PETmonofil	PETmonofil	-
Hr1	Hexagonal	PET/ramie-viscose	PETmonofil	-
Hr2	Hexagonal	PET/ramie-viscose	PETmonofil	-
Hr3	Hexagonal	PET/ramie-viscose	PETmultifil	-
Hpg1	Hexagonal	PET/polyester	PETmultifil	204 tex glass knitted
Hpg2	Hexagonal	PET/polyester	PETmultifil	68 tex glass inserted

In Table 1, three families of materials can be distinguished. The first two types of knits are the plain PET-monofilament knittings as produced for textile applications. The newly developed Hr-types all have PET/ramie-viscose pile fibers, while the Hpg-types have PET/polyester piles and extra glass fibers in their skins. Two versions of Hpg-knits are available: one with the glass knitted into the skins while the other version has the glass inserted as straight bundles.

It is clear that the knits with combined yarns will have higher mechanical properties because they can be impregnated better, especially the pile fibers.

Production of composite samples

Two types of resin systems have been used for the production of composite samples. Resin1 is a sheet like resin that has to be cured in an oven for 60 minutes at 125°C. The other one, resin2 is a solvent based resin which cures at room temperature in open air after evaporation of the solvent. This second type gives better homogenisation of the resin.

All composite samples have a thickness around 7mm. Only the samples Hpg2-a and Hpg2-b are thinner (5.5mm).

Bending properties

In Fig. 9, the apparent bending modulus of 3D-knitted composites has been shown. The main orientation angle of the beam elements (which is in fact the main fiber orientation) and the resin content are mentioned. In this figure, two groups of composites can be distinguished. The samples on the left hand side of the figure have been impregnated with resin1, the others with resin2.

Fig. 9: Bending modulus of 3D-knitted composites

In the left group all samples have about the same degree of stretching so that they are comparable in this respect. Samples H10 and R7 are the first generation of 3D-knitted composites: they are knitted from plain PET-monofilaments which are difficult to impregnate properly. This is also the reason why the modulus of H10 is low: the pile fibers are barely impregnated.

The value for R7 is already much higher because the sample has a high resin content. In this case the skins are well impregnated and on some spots even over-impregnated, while the pile fibers of R7 are getting impregnated as well due to the abundance of resin. As a consequence of this, resin walls between the piles are being formed. This drastically increases the stiffness of the composite. Resin lumps in the corners between the piles and the skins have the same effect.

Samples Hr1, Hr2, Hr3 are all based on PET/ramie-viscose pile fibers which means that the core is much better impregnated and the properties are higher. However, these three types of samples, especially Hr1 and Hr3 have been over-impregnated. The corners between beam elements and the corners between piles and skin have been filled with resin, which drastically increases the stiffness.

Comparing these three samples with Hr2 and Hr3 impregnated with resin2 shows that the latter are somewhat stiffer despite the lower resin content. The reason for this is that they have been stretched more. However, one would expect the difference to be bigger, but this is not so

because of over-impregnation of the samples with resin1 and because resin1 is stiffer than resin2.

The effect of stretching the knittings becomes more clear in the Hpg-samples. They are all impregnated with the same resin2 but also, the resin content for samples made from one type of knit is constant (58 or 65w%) for both the stretched and the unstretched versions. The stretched samples (~21°) clearly are stiffer, they have a stiffness of about double that of the less stretched ones (~33°).

In Fig. 10 the apparent bending modulus versus the density of the composite is visualised. All available samples have been put into two categories, although there is some variation in the measured angle. There is a group of samples which are highly stretched (~21°) and samples which are less stretched (~33°). Both the warp and weft direction are presented.

Fig.10: Apparent bending modulus versus composite density

For each group of samples a linear relationship between modulus and density is observed. Modulus goes up with increasing density of the composite but also depends on the degree of stretching. The type of knitting yarn does not seem to have a lot of influence nor does the resin. This would suggest that the stiffness is mainly dependent on the geometry of the unit cells and on the density, just like foam materials. Of course, all results presented here are the first findings based on just a small number of samples. It is still too early to draw general conclusions.

However, one limitation of the current analysis is the artificial division of the composite samples into two categories. A more correct way is to perform a normalisation for the degree of stretching and to have a look at more samples that only differ in angle.

A variation of a few degrees was recorded when characterising the samples. This will not have such a big influence on the samples that have their beam elements at an angle of 33°. However, it becomes much more critical for samples that are more stretched. This is probably

the reason why the extra glass in the skins of Hpg-knits seems to be inefficient at first sight. Another reason is that part of the glass fibers are broken because of knitting and these broken fibers could be seen on the sample. It is also obvious that if the Hpg-samples with 24° would have been normalised to an angle of about 20°, the apparent E_b -modulus would be higher.

CONCLUSIONS

1. 3D-knitted fabrics are being adapted to satisfy specific needs of composites and new types of complex yarns are under investigation.
2. Stretching the fabric can be used to control the stiffness of the composite.
3. A reliable method for comparing test specimen with different degrees of stretching is necessary.

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